

Suspended sediment connectivity analysis: Snowmelt-driven dynamics in an alpine basin

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ABSTRACT

Understanding snowmelt and its related suspended sediment transport in mountain streams is a crucial issue in the world of hydraulic and sediment research. Field-based approaches are still poorly used to investigate the response of mountain basins to different stages of snowmelt. To explain the suspended sediment dynamics of the Rio Cordon basin (Italy, Dolomites), the snowmelt in the year 2021 was analysed. First, a descriptive analysis of temporal trends of meteorological, hydrological, and sedimentological variables was carried out. Second, suspended sediment budgets of the main channel were quantified, considering the contribution of the tributaries at week- and event- scale, and supported by hysteresis analyses. Third, the role of sediment sources and snow cover was examined and integrated to comprehend variations in sediment supply from tributaries. Data were collected using a (i) multiparametric sonde installed at the outlet, (ii) water and sediment samples at significant points along the channel network, (iii) satellite images and sediment sources inventory. The whole snowmelt period 2021 featured 210.8 mm of precipitation and a mean temperature of 4.6°C. The total load of suspended sediment was 100 t. The main period of ablation was May, which showed contrasting suspended sediment dynamics in the four weeks. Sediment availability exceeded transport capacity in the initial two weeks, whereas transport capacity exceeded sediment availability in the subsequent two weeks. The main snowmelt event analysis mirrored the same trend: limited transport during the rising limb and the opposite during the falling limb. Such results were confirmed by the hysteresis analysis, proving to be an effective tool for detecting changes in suspended sediment connectivity. The variations of snow cover and the extent of sediment sources across the sub-basins influence the sediment supply. This study enhances our comprehension of snowmelt-driven hydrological and sedimentological dynamics, providing insights into the resilience of mountains to changing climate conditions.

1. Introduction

Alpine mountain basins typically receive large amounts of snow that play an important role in feeding and triggering flood events during the snowmelt season (Lana-Renault et al., 2011). Besides influencing the chemical and ecological characteristics of mountain streams (Williams and Melack, 1991; Soulsby et al., 1997), the ablation process can drive geomorphological processes such as shallow land sliding, rilling, and sheet-wash erosion that contribute to the sediment yield (Barsch and Caine, 1984). Among the different sediment transport processes occurring in a mountain stream, suspended sediment is commonly considered to be of secondary importance with respect to other phenomena such as bedload, hyperconcentrated flows and debris flows (Lenzi et al., 2003),

it can contribute to the total sediment load from 70 to 90 % in lowland rivers (Lane and Borland, 1951; Walling and Webb, 1987) and between 37 to 100 % in Alpine streams (Durst, 1990; Lauffer and Sommer, 1982; Lenzi et al., 2003). Especially in mountain basins with abundant sediment sources, suspended load can exceed bedload transport and determine water quality (Wohl, 2010), aquatic habitats and channel morphology (Lenzi et al., 2003). Suspended sediment availability and transport loads feature inter- and intra-seasonal variations. Lana-Renault et al. (2011), for example, found that snowmelt season contributed to the 60 % of the total suspended sediment load in the period 2003–2006 in the Central Spanish Pyrenees, while Rainato et al. (2017), in the Cordon Stream (Italy), reported a 70 % fraction for the period 2003–2014 but only 37.3 % for the entire period 1986–2014. As

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far as the snowmelt season is concerned, [Bogen \(1995\)](#) showed temporal variations on Norwegian rivers among suspended sediment concentrations generated during the flood events of the early ($<40 \text{ mg l}^{-1}$), central ($50\text{--}100 \text{ mg l}^{-1}$) and final ($>500 \text{ mg l}^{-1}$) snowmelt period. The end of the snowmelt season is generally the most complex in terms of hydrological and sediment transport processes, since the combination of snow melting and rainfall can trigger rain-on-snow events ([Lenzi et al., 2003](#); [Rainato et al., 2018](#)). In addition to the differences in temporality and types of hydrological processes generating snowmelt flood events, variations in sediment load may also result from the contribution patterns of sediment sources. In fact, depending on whether the contribution originates from the main channel, tributaries, or hillslopes, the peak of suspended sediment concentration can occur before, during or after the peak of liquid discharge ([Kurashige, 1994](#); [Lenzi and Marchi, 2000](#); [Lenzi et al., 2003](#); [Zabaleta et al., 2007](#); [De Girolamo et al., 2015](#); [Cheraghi et al., 2016](#); [Misset et al., 2019](#); [Pellegrini et al., 2023](#)). If the peak of suspended sediment load does not coincide with the peak of liquid discharge, a hysteretic pattern can be recognized, and the hysteresis loops ([Millares and Moñino, 2020](#)) allow to infer the mechanisms of suspended sediment delivery, landscape connectivity ([Gregory and Walling, 1973](#); [Lenzi and Marchi, 2000](#); [Pietroni et al., 2015](#)) and spatial distribution of the main sediment sources. Hysteresis loops are clockwise when the peak of suspended sediment transport occurs before the liquid peak discharge, and this has been attributed to conditions in which the sediments come from sources close to the basin's outlet ([Asselman et al., 2003](#); [De Girolamo et al., 2015](#)). In the opposite case, counterclockwise loops occur when sediment sources are far from the outlet ([Williams, 1989](#); [Kurashige, 1994](#); [Seeger et al., 2004](#)). Hysteresis can also be rather weak, when either the sediment availability is unlimited or the processes generating sediment flows and water discharges are synchronized ([López-Tarazón and Estrany, 2017](#)). An increasing number of studies recently reported on the hysteresis patterns of floods with suspended sediment transport, and there are several sophisticated indexes to quantitatively determine their magnitude (e.g., [Zuecco et al., 2016](#); [Hamshaw et al., 2018](#); [Aich et al., 2014](#)). However, the interpretation of the processes determining the hysteresis patterns is still rather speculative, and the spatial-temporal variations of suspended sediments dynamics in the river network are not considered enough. In this sense, understanding the linkages between tributaries and the main river network, in fact, could reveal the channel network's sediment routing dynamics ([Knighton, 1989](#); [Benda and Dunne, 1997](#); [Rice, 1998](#); [Brierley and Fryirs, 1999](#); [Mosley and Schumm, 2001](#); [Brierley et al., 2006](#); [Fryirs et al., 2007](#); [Fryirs, 2013](#)).

To date, significant attention has been paid towards analysing the seasonal trends of snowmelt, with a primary focus on hydrology and soil erosion ([Wu and Fang, 2024](#)). Despite these efforts, a noticeable gap in the literature remains: the absence of an intense and comprehensive field analysis that focuses on the distinct phases characterizing the different temporal and spatial responses of mountain basins during snowmelt. Particularly, a lack of research in understanding the specific mechanisms and dynamics governing suspended sediment fluxes and budgets in tributaries and channel reaches within alpine basins during snowmelt periods is still present. Despite the long-term monitoring program, this knowledge gap remains evident even in the Rio Cordon basin. Analyses in this area have predominantly focused on basin-scale assessments at decadal, annual, or seasonal intervals since 1987. This knowledge gap underscored the need for further field-based investigations to better understand the processes driving sediment routing, which cause temporal fluctuations in suspended sediment contributions across various spatial scales, and the identification of sediment sources influencing suspended sediment throughout the season of snowmelt. Therefore, this work aims at investigating suspended sediment fluxes and budgets in tributaries and channel reaches, employing hysteresis analyses to explain sediment routing within an alpine basin during the 2021 snowmelt period. To do so, the study involves three primary analyses: (i) providing an initial overview of the

ablation season in 2021, (ii) examining the weekly and daily contributions of suspended sediment at the event scale, along with budgeting for main reaches of the Rio Cordon, and (iii) investigating the role of sediment sources in contributing to the suspended sediment throughout the examined snowmelt season.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Study area

The alpine Rio Cordon basin has an extension of 5 km^2 and is located in the Northeast of Italy ([Fig. 1A](#)). Its elevation ranges from 1763 m a.s.l. to 2763 m a.s.l., and the mean slope is around 27° .

Alpine pastures (54 %) , bare lands (38 %) and norway spruce forests (8 %) cover the basin ([Martini et al., 2022](#)). From a geological point of view, dolomite and volcanic rocks compose the upper part of the catchment (Wengen formation) while sandstones and calcareous-marly rocks feature the lower part (Buchenstein formation). The presence of a waterfall in the middle of the basin creates a prominent disconnection between upstream and downstream generating different responses in terms of sediment dynamics and fluxes ([Oss Cazzador et al., 2020](#); [Pellegrini et al., 2021](#)). The upstream river features a plane-bed morphology, whereas the downstream Rio Cordon is characterized by cascade, step-pool and riffle-pool morphologies ([Montgomery and Buffington, 1997](#); [Picco et al., 2020](#)). The hydrological regime of the catchment is nivo-pluvial, featuring short and intense rainfall during spring and summer, with snowfall during late autumn and winter. Therefore, during the later part of the snowmelt period (May – June), it is common to have rain-on-snow flood events. To characterize the basin from a climatic, hydrological and sedimentological point of view, a long-term permanent station was installed in 1985 ([Fattorelli et al., 1988](#)). The long-term monitoring defined the bankfull width and discharge as 5.3 m and $2.3 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, respectively ([Lenzi et al., 2006](#); [Rainato et al., 2020](#)). Since November 2018 the station stopped working due to the occurrence of a large flood event, the Vaia rainstorm (more info in [Rainato et al., 2021](#); [Pellegrini et al., 2023](#)). In the Rio Cordon, the mean annual precipitation (1986–2018) and temperature (2010–2021) is around 1180 mm and 3.9°C , respectively. The snowmelt seasons (1st April–15th June, [Rainato et al., 2017](#)) recorded since 1987 featured a mean temperature of 7.8°C and a mean total precipitation of 277 mm ([Fig. 2](#)).

The Rio Cordon is characterized by the presence of four distinct tributaries, denoted in the following work as T1, T2, T3, and T4 ([Table 1](#); [Fig. 1](#)). Tributaries T1 and T2 are located to the West/Northwest, with elevation ranging between 2564.5–1981.7 m a.s.l. and 2384.0–1934.5 m a.s.l., respectively. In contrast, tributaries T3 and T4 are situated to the East/Northeast, with elevations ranging between 2438.3–1923.5 m a.s.l. and 2566.2–1835.4 m a.s.l., respectively. Within the context of this study, worth highlighting are the sub-reaches positioned between the confluences of the mentioned tributaries, designated as SR1, SR2, SR3, and SR4, arranged in sequence from upstream to downstream ([Fig. 1](#), [Table 1](#)). SR1, spanning 451 m, exhibits a slope of 12 %. Likewise, SR2, covering a length of 153 m, features a 12 % slope. Advancing downstream, SR3 demonstrates a steeper slope of 15 % and extends over a length of 336 m. Finally, a shorter length of 88 m characterizes SR4, with an 11 % slope.

2.2. Data collection and laboratory measurements

A multiparameter sonde (Hydrolab HL4) and a pressure transducer sensor were used to measure turbidity and water level at the outlet of the basin at 15-minute resolutions (SR4, [Fig. 1B](#)). To transform turbidity and water level into suspended sediment concentration (SSC, in g l^{-1}) and water discharge (Q, in m^3/s), two power-law empirical regressions were used (see [Pellegrini et al., 2023](#)). Air temperature (T) and precipitation (P) were retrieved hourly by a meteorological station located close to

Fig. 1. (A) Location of the Rio Cordon in Italy and a map showing its tributaries with their drainage areas (T1, T2, T3, and T4). (B) Channel sub-reaches (SR0, SR1, SR2, SR3, and SR4) where suspended sediment budgets were computed using yields measured along the tributaries (orange arrows) and in the channel reaches downstream of the confluences (black arrows). The uppermost black arrow will be defined as SR0 as it represents only a monitoring site and not a sub-reach in which computing the budget. The yellow light bulb indicates the outlet of the basin where a multiparameter sonde continuously monitors turbidity.

Fig. 2. Mean temperature (T, A) and total precipitation (B) of the snowmelt periods registered since 1987. The dark dots represent the mean temperature and total precipitation of snowmelt 2021.

Table 1

Main characteristics of the tributaries and channel reaches analysed in the Rio Cordon basin.

	Aspect	Elevation range (m a.s.l.)	Area (m ²)
T1	West/Northwest	2564.5–1981.7	87089.8
T2	West/Northwest	2384.0–1934.5	48801.1
T3	East/Northeast	2438.3–1923.5	13480.8
T4	East/Northeast	2566.2–1835.4	8789.0
	Slope (%)	Length (m)	Bankfull width (m)
SR1	12	451	12.3
SR2	12	153	17.9
SR3	15	336	12.1
SR4	11	88	20.4

Table 2

Percentiles (D₁₀, D₅₀ and D₉₀) of the Grain Size Distribution (GSD) analyses taken on the sediment samples of the four tributaries.

	T1	T2	T3	T4
D ₁₀	8.07 μm	25.8 μm	4.58 μm	5.26 μm
D ₅₀	66.8 μm	155 μm	34.1 μm	41.9 μm
D ₉₀	314 μm	515 μm	120 μm	167 μm

SR4. This station is managed by ARPA Veneto and is equipped with a heated rain gauge (PPI 081 model, MTX Italia S.r.l. company). In addition to the data measured in continuity at the outlet of the basin with the multiparameter sonde, during the four weeks of May 2021 (1st-7th, 8th-15th, 16th- 23rd, 24th- 31st), intensive field campaigns were carried out to collect data of Q and SSC in the tributaries (T1, T2, T3, T4; Fig. 1B, Table 1;) and in the main channel reaches (SR1, SR2, SR3, SR4; Fig. 1B, Table 1). Data was collected once a week at three times a day (i. e. morning, afternoon and evening). Furthermore, during the main flood event, data collection was made at higher sampling intervals, i.e. at consecutive days still three times a day, to further characterize the phases of raising, peak and falling of the event. Data collection stopped during the last week of May as the remaining snow was limited to a marginal area. For this reason, flood events after the 30th of May were not considered in the budgeting analyses. For each week, each tributary and each sub-reach, a mean daily Q and SSC was calculated. The daily suspended sediment load (SSL, in kg ha⁻¹ d⁻¹) was computed by multiplying the corresponding mean daily SSC (g l⁻¹) by the mean daily Q converted in l s⁻¹. The discharge of the tributaries and of the channel reaches was measured using the salt dilution technique following the procedure of Moore (2005). To this end, a portable conductivity meter (WTW Cond340i) was used at each monitoring site. A variable quantity of 0.25 and 0.5 kg of NaCl mixed with stream water in a bucket was used as tracer (Comiti et al., 2007). Once diluted, the tracer was released 25 m upstream the monitoring site and the water conductivity was measured to record the salt wave. After determining the calibration constant *k*, the discharge was computed following the approach proposed by Moore, (2005) as:

$$Q = \frac{V}{k \Delta t \sum_n [EC(t) - EC_{bg}]} \quad (1)$$

where V is the volume of salt solution injected (l), *k* the calibration constant and $\sum_n [EC(t) - EC_{bg}]$ is the resulting changes in electrical conductivity (EC, μS/cm) at intervals of Δ*t* until EC returns to the initial level. EC_{bg} indicates the background electrical conductivity of the stream. To provide information on the suspended sediment concentration, instead, water samples were collected in 1-liter plastic bottles. The material was filtered, dried at 105 °C and weighted in the laboratory in order to obtain the concentration of suspended sediment in g l⁻¹ (Pellegrini et al., 2023). Moreover, to obtain information concerning the grain size distribution (GSD) of the sediment samples collected along the sub-basins, the Mastersizer 3000 laser particle size analyser (Malvern

Panalytical, Malvern) with Hydro wet dispersion unit (Abdulkarim et al., 2021) was employed. To enhance the reliability of the GSD results, all sediment samples collected during the period of interest were merged while maintaining the subdivision into sub-basins. Therefore, the final value of the Grain Size Distribution (GSD) represents the average of the sediment transported during May 2021 in each sub-basin. The Mie optical model was used to compute the GSD. In the measurement, the wet dispersion unit was filled with 500 ml of water. The system was aligned, capturing background signals, which were then subtracted from particle size measurements. The sample was gradually added until it reached 10–20 % obscuration range. To break down soil aggregates, 320 s of active ultrasound was applied (Ryžak and Bieganowski, 2011). Five 30-second measurement runs were conducted for each sample, and the resulting mean from these runs was selected as the final value (Kubínová et al., 2021). To describe the GSD information, the D₁₀, D₅₀ and D₉₀ percentile of each sub-basin distribution was presented.

2.3. Data analysis

First, a descriptive analysis of temporal trends of P, T, Q, SSC, and SSL was carried out in the main Rio Cordon channel throughout the entire snowmelt period spanning from April to June. In this part, data concerning SSC were solely retrieved by the multiparameter sonde installed at the outlet of the basin (Fig. 1B). Second, the investigation focused on the four weeks of May 2021 including weekly and event-based analyses. Main channel and tributaries were considered in this investigation. Notably, data collected at each confluence along the main channel and at each tributary enabled the computation of the suspended sediment budget for each reach during various phases of the ablation season excluding SR0, which solely and exclusively represents the initial monitoring point (Fig. 1). The suspended sediment budget for each reach was determined by subtracting the SSL value measured at the nearest downstream monitoring location from the value measured at the nearest upstream monitoring site. Eq.2 shows the mathematical computation of the budget which is given by:

$$SRx_{budget} = (SSL_{SRx-1} + SSL_{Tx}) - SSL_{SRx} \quad (2)$$

Where SRx_{budget} indicates the sub-reach for which we intend to calculate the budget, SSL_{SRx-1} represents the suspended sediment load recorded at the end of the upstream sub-reach, SSL_{Tx} is the suspended sediment load recorded at the tributary entering the sub-reach for which the budget is to be calculated, and SSL_{SRx} is the suspended sediment load measured at the end of the sub-reach of interest. For instance, the computation of the budget for SR2 involved subtracting the SSL measured in SR2 from the sum of SSL measured in SR1 and T2 (Eq.2; Fig. 1). This process facilitated the identification of whether the reaches underwent sediment deficit (i.e., indicating erosion) or surplus (i.e., indicating deposition). To enhance the understanding and assessment of the dynamics and transport capacity of the Rio Cordon, a hysteresis analysis was applied at both weekly and daily scales. This analysis utilized the mean weekly discharge (Q_m) and mean weekly SSC (g l⁻¹). Additionally, the study delved into data concerning the duration (days) of raising, peak and falling phases of the main snowmelt flood, aiming to provide a detailed description of the runoff and suspended sediment dynamics. Concurrently, the SSL for each tributary and the suspended sediment budget along the confluences of the main channel for each phase of the flood event were computed. Third, the inventory of sediment sources at the scale of the entire basin (Martini et al., 2022) was used to identify and count the number of sediment sources potentially contributing to each tributary investigated in this study. The database counted 133 sediment sources covering the four sub-basins of interest and were classified as stream bank erosion, landslides, debris flow channels or surficial erosion. The extent of snow cover during the study period was mapped using a series of satellite images provided by the Planet satellite imaging system. Specifically, a series of five images with a weekly collection

frequency at 3x3 m spatial resolution were obtained from the Planet website (<https://www.planet.com>) and used to calculate the variation in snow cover during May 2021. The selection of images was run with a maximum cloud cover of 30 %. Snow cover data were used to map and calculate the percentage of sediment source areas covered by snow to further support the suspended sediment transport results. Data was processed and analysed using GIS software (QGIS 3.28 and ArcGIS Pro 3.0) and RStudio v2022.02.

3. Results

3.1. Snowmelt 2021: General description and main flood events

During the 2021 snowmelt season in the Rio Cordon basin (1st April–15th June), the mean temperature recorded was 5.1 °C, with a range between –10.0 °C and 22.6 °C. This period stands out as the second coldest snowmelt observed since 1987, varying more than 2 °C from the average of 7.8 °C. The total precipitation registered was 210.8 mm, with maximum intensities of 4.6 mm in 1 h, 11.0 mm in 3 h, and 26.0 mm in 24 h. The total precipitation was lower compared to the 277 mm average of the period 1987–2021 (Fig. 2). The mean discharge reached 0.52 m³/s, with a minimum and maximum of 0.14 and 1.63 m³/s. The mean SSC was 0.03 g l⁻¹, while the maximum was measured as 0.16 g l⁻¹. The total suspended load computed at the outlet of the basin was 100 t during the entire ablation season.

From a hydrological point of view, the 2021 snowmelt season featured two main events, respectively, in the first and second week of May (Fig. 3). Both events were triggered by a combination of rain and snow melting. During the first event, Q peaked at 1.0 m³/s, with a total P of 30.8 mm and a SSL of around 12.7 t. The maximum SSC and the mean temperature were registered as 0.09 g l⁻¹ and 2.6 °C. The second event displayed a Q peak of 1.63 m³/s, a total P of 37 mm, and a SSL of 18 t. The maximum value of SSC was 0.08 g l⁻¹ while the mean temperature was approximately 4.6 °C.

3.2. Ablation's month: hydrological, climatic and weekly sediment budgeting, dynamics and fluxes

May was the main month of the 2021 ablation season with a mean daily T ranging from 1.8 °C to 7.3 °C and a cumulative precipitation of

131.6 mm. The mean Q of the month was 0.5 m³/s.

As far as the four weeks of May 2021 are concerned, it is worth highlighting their different hydrological and climatic conditions. The coldest week was week 1 (1st–7th May) with a mean daily T of 2.6 °C. The warmest was week 2 (8th–14th May), with a mean daily T of 4.6 °C and a daily maximum of 14.9 °C. The same week registered the highest value of mean Q (0.81 m³s⁻¹). On the contrary, the lowest value of mean Q (0.32 m³/s) was measured during the 3rd week (15th–21st May) which also recorded the lowest precipitation (25.8 mm) in the four weeks. In contrast, week 4 (22nd–28th May) experienced the highest amount of rainfall reaching a cumulative value of 39.6 mm. However, the mean Q of this last week was in line with the one of week 3, i.e. around 0.34 m³/s. Overall, the mean suspended sediment yield of the period detected at the outlet of the basin was 3.8 kg ha⁻¹ d⁻¹. In the tributaries, week 1 featured suspended sediment yields constantly < 0.5 kg ha⁻¹ d⁻¹, with the exception of the T4 tributary that contributed 39.49 kg ha⁻¹ d⁻¹ (Table 3, Fig. 4). In the same period, the main channel sediment budget showed evidence of suspended sediment surplus (i.e., deposition), especially in SR4 where the calculated budget was 39.91 kg ha⁻¹ d⁻¹ (Table 3). However, the suspended sediment determined in SR3 budget, indicated sediment deficit, i.e., erosion, with a negative value of –2.68 kg ha⁻¹ d⁻¹. The suspended sediment yield detected at the outlet was 2.93 kg ha⁻¹ d⁻¹. In the second week, instead, higher values of suspended sediment loads were recorded all along the investigated portion of the basin, from the reaches of the main channel to the tributaries. All the main channel reaches (SR1, SR2, SR3 and SR4) experienced an excess of sediment, i.e., evident deposition (Table 3). The suspended sediment yield detected at the outlet was 15.85 kg ha⁻¹ d⁻¹. The third week of the ablation season featured a different dynamic, especially moving from upstream to downstream. While the upper part of the basin (T1 and T2) contributed scarcely to the sediment budget, the lower part (T3 and T2) provided huge amounts of suspended sediment. Only one sub-reach featured a negative sediment budget (Table 3). This prevalence of erosive conditions was documented in SR1, i.e., the most upper reach. SR2, instead, registered neither deposition nor erosion. Conversely, the two remaining reaches featured a large range of positive budgets, ranging from 8.38 kg ha⁻¹ d⁻¹ in SR4 to over 20 kg ha⁻¹ d⁻¹ in SR3. The suspended sediment yield detected at the outlet was 8.38 kg ha⁻¹ d⁻¹. Lastly, week 4 recorded the lowest contributing period of May 2021 as none of the tributaries showed a suspended sediment load

Fig. 3. (A) Temperature (T, blue line), moving average value of the temperature in 24 h (dark blue dotted line), precipitation (P, green columns), (B) water discharge (Q, black line) and suspended sediment concentration (SSC, brown columns) experienced by the Rio Cordon from 1st April to 15th June 2021. The time resolution of T, P, Q and SSC was 15 min. The red rectangles indicate the four weeks in which the analysis focused on week and event-scale.

Table 3

Summary of the mean values of the hydrological and sedimentological variables recorded along the SRs and the four tributaries of the Rio Cordon: Discharge (Q), Suspended Sediment Concentration (SSC) and Suspended Sediment Load (SSL). For the SSL, the table also shows the variable $SSL_{SRx-1} + SSL_{Tx}$ needed for budget computations.

	SSC (mg l^{-1})				Q (m^3/s)				SSL ($\text{Kg ha}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$)			
	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4
SR0	2.12	4.01	2.21	2.80	0.16	0.46	0.18	0.25	0.13	0.68	0.15	0.26
T1	8.00	11.00	2.00	2.00	0.05	0.08	0.03	0.04	0.50	1.73	0.06	0.11
SR0 + T1									0.63	2.41	0.20	0.37
SR1	7.08	9.84	6.32	2.14	0.20	0.55	0.21	0.29	0.38	1.42	0.34	0.17
Budget SR1									0.25	0.99	-0.14	0.20
T2	7.00	39.00	3.00	4.00	0.02	0.06	0.03	0.03	0.09	4.34	0.18	0.27
SR1 + T2									0.47	5.76	0.53	0.43
SR2	9.09	17.88	9.45	15.39	0.23	0.73	0.24	0.31	0.47	2.81	0.53	2.08
Budget SR2									0.00	2.95	0.00	-1.65
T3	2.00	55.00	5.00	9.00	0.02	0.03	0.44	0.02	0.19	10.75	21.53	1.65
T3 + SR2									0.67	13.56	22.05	3.72
SR3	36.68	53.94	32.45	57.34	0.47	0.75	0.27	0.32	3.35	7.94	1.71	4.39
Budget SR3									-2.68	5.62	20.35	-0.67
T4	130.00	40.00	120.00	20.00	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.01	39.49	15.30	9.03	2.23
T4 + SR3bis									42.84	23.24	10.73	6.62
SR4	32.81	36.57	38.82	36.59	0.52	1.17	0.35	0.40	2.93	7.39	2.36	2.54
Budget SR4									39.91	15.85	8.38	4.08

Fig. 4. Representation of the tributaries contribution (orange) and of the sediment deficit (red) or surplus occurring along the main channel reaches during the 4 weeks of May 2021. The thickness of the tributaries' polyline indicates the amount of sediment transported.

particularly high. During this week, two SRs featured deposition (SR1 and SR4) and two erosions (SR2 and SR3). The suspended sediment yield detected at the outlet was $4.08 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$ during week 4.

In general, the particle size distribution of the suspended sediment transported along the sub-basins showed substantial differences, especially between T1-T2 and T3-T4 (Table 2). Among the tributaries, T2 recorded the highest values for D_{10} and D_{90} at $25.8 \mu\text{m}$ and $515 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. T3, on the other hand, exhibited the highest value for D_{50} .

Conversely, the lowest values for D_{50} and D_{90} were observed in T1 at $66.8 \mu\text{m}$ and $314 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. The smallest D_{10} was found in T3 at $4.58 \mu\text{m}$.

As to the hysteresis analysis, it is worth comparing the results obtained at the outlet (downstream reach 4) of the basin (Fig. 5a) with those recorded along the four tributaries (Fig. 5b). The basin featured a clockwise loop showing an unsynchronized discharge peak in respect to the peak of suspended sediment concentration. In fact, the former

Fig. 5. (A) Weekly hysteresis loops computed at the outlet of the basin and (B) in the four tributaries. The thick blue arrow indicates the direction of the loops.

reached its maximum in the 2nd week, while the latter during the 4th. On the other hand, the hysteresis loops observed in the tributaries showed both strong clockwise and weak behaviors. In the former case (T3), the peak of sediment concentrations anticipates the peak of discharge, while in the latter case (T1 and T2) the two peaks occurred approximately simultaneously. T4 shows a very weak hysteresis loop. It is worth highlighting that all tributaries, except for T4, featured the highest peak in suspended sediment concentration during the 2nd week. On the contrary, the peak discharge varied between the 2nd (T1 and T2) and the 3rd week (T3 and T4).

3.3. Ablation event: Investigation of climatic, hydrological and sedimentary conditions at daily scale

During the 2021 ablation period, the event with the highest discharge lasted between the 8th and 15th of May. Specifically, the peak of discharged measured at the outlet reached $1.63 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ and was recorded on 12th May. The first day of the analysis (11th May) registered 18.8 mm of precipitation, a mean and maximum daily T of $5.4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

and $10.4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively. The second day, when the peak was reached, recorded a lower daily P (8.4 mm), but higher mean and maximum T, $6.4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $17.4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively. Nevertheless, the mean daily Q was higher than the first day and reached $1.44 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. During the falling limb, on the 13th May, both the daily P and mean Q dropped to 1.6 mm and $0.87 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, respectively. However, the mean and maximum daily T increased up to $7.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $19.8 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Table 4 shows that the three days under investigation featured high-suspended sediment contribution from all four tributaries. Such high sediment supply from the tributaries promoted high deposition all along the main channel reaches especially during day 1 in SR3 and SR4, where the sediment budget exceeded $19 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$ (Fig. 6). The day of the peak (12th May) proved to be less dynamic from the point of view of the sediment contribution, being only $7.31 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$ the highest value recorded along the tributaries (Table 4). It is interesting to note that the middle reach SR3 featured a general tendency to erosion, showing a negative budget of $-3.07 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$. The third day of the event (13th May), representing the falling limb of the hydrograph, featured a rather different dynamic if compared to the two previous days. On the one

Table 4

Summary of the mean values of the hydrological and sedimentological variables recorded along the SRs and the four tributaries of the Rio Cordon during the main event of snowmelt 2021: Discharge (Q), Suspended Sediment Concentration (SSC) and Suspended Sediment Load (SSL). For the SSL, the table shows also the variable $SSL_{SRx-1} + SSL_{Tx}$ needed for the budget computations.

	SSC (mg l^{-1})			Q (m^3/s)			SSL ($\text{Kg ha}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$)		
	11/05	12/05	13/05	11/05	12/05	13/05	11/05	12/05	13/05
SR0	0.00	3.85	4.35	0.00	0.62	0.30	0.00	0.89	0.48
T1	26.25	9.85	1.05	0.08	0.17	0.33	2.69	2.07	0.42
Up + T1							2.69	2.96	0.90
SR1	9.85	13.15	2.04	0.76	0.25	0.63	1.97	0.88	0.34
Budget SR1							0.72	2.08	0.56
T2	106.95	3.85	4.35	0.06	0.07	0.05	12.08	0.50	0.43
SR1 + T2							14.05	1.37	0.77
SR2	6.85	6.95	9.75	0.90	0.69	0.68	1.78	1.04	1.33
Budget SR2							12.27	0.33	0.56
T3	92.15	22.05	9.35	0.03	0.03	0.02	24.99	5.80	1.80
T3 + SR2							26.76	6.84	3.13
SR3	39.02	48.542	33.35	0.90	1.04	0.86	6.83	9.91	5.62
Budget SR3							19.93	-3.07	-2.49
T4	70.85	37.25	11.55	0.03	0.02	0.01	23.29	7.31	1.45
T4 + SR3							30.12	17.22	7.08
SR4	40.19	35.06	37.85	1.22	1.44	0.87	8.45	8.43	5.29
Budget SR4							21.67	8.79	1.78

Fig. 6. Representation of the tributaries contribution (orange) and of the sediment deficit (red) or surplus occurring along the main channel reaches during the main event of snowmelt period. The thickness of the tributary's polyline indicates the amount of sediment transported.

Fig. 7. Representation of snow cover during snowmelt (From 1st to 30th May 2021) across the four sub-basins (T1, T2, T3 and T4). Red polygons indicate the sediment source areas, while the white gap between the upstream and downstream part of the Rio Cordon is a graphical way to represent the disconnection of the lower part of the basin.

hand, the suspended sediment contribution of the four tributaries was prominently lower ($<1.80 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$) (Table 4), and on the other hand, one out of four reaches was recorded in a general tendency of sediment deficit ($-2.49 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$) (Fig. 6). However, none of the SRs presenting sediment surplus showed particularly high positive budgets.

3.4. Connecting the dots: Snow cover and sediment sources

The inventory of sediment sources at the scale of the entire basin allowed identifying and counting the number of sediment sources potentially contributing to each tributary investigated in this study. The sub-basin drained by T1 featured 52 sediment sources classified mainly as landslides and debris flow channels. The total area of T1 sediment sources is 87089.78 m^2 , corresponding to 12.25 % of the total sub-basin area. On the other hand, T2 is characterized by 62 sediment sources, covering 48801.10 m^2 and 10.74 % of the sub-basin. Landslides were the main sources of sediment. As for T3 and T4, the number of sediment sources is reduced to 8 and 11, covering 13480.79 and 8789.04 m^2 , respectively. However, the percentage cover is higher if compared to the previous ones and represents 15.07 % and 12.52 %, respectively. In both cases most sediment sources were debris flows channels. Fig. 7 shows the significant changes in snow cover of the sediment sources draining the tributaries during May 2021. At the beginning of the month, May 1st, 2021, the percentage of sediment sources covered by snow was 96.7 % and 90.71 % for T1 and T2, respectively. For T3 and T4, however, the percentages were lower, at 76.41 % and 52.70 %, respectively. After the first week, T1 and T2 remained at 96.70 % and 90.70 % of snow cover, respectively. On the contrary, the percentage started to decrease in T3 and T4, registering 70.49 % and 42.79 %, respectively.

Midway through the month, May 16th, 2021, the percentages remained quite high in T1 and T2 (96.68 % and 75.21 %), but continued to decrease for T3 and T4, with percentage values reaching 61.34 % and 33.22 %. During the last week, May 26th, 2021, the snow cover over the sediment sources remained approximately the same in T1 (95.87 %) but started to change in T2 (75.21 %). In T3 and T4, the snow continued to melt, reaching a coverage of 22.78 % and 26 %. Finally, at the end of the month, May 30th, 2021, significant values of snow melting were recorded, except for T1, which remained at around 91.12 %. As for T2, T3, and T4, the coverage percentages over the sediment sources reached values of 33.81 %, 19.37 %, and 13.96 %, respectively. Comparing the average weekly values of suspended solid transport ($\text{kg ha}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$) with the snowmelt percentages from the contributing areas of each sub-basin, it is evident that the basins experiencing higher rates of snowmelt also

exhibited greater sediment transport during the ablation month (May 2021). The SSL trends of T4 and T3 align closely with the temporal melting percentage of their respective basins (Fig. 8). In contrast, sub-basin T1, which underwent minimal snowmelt throughout almost the entire period until reaching the source areas, demonstrates significantly lower values in suspended sediment transport.

4. Discussions

4.1. Snowmelt and sediment dynamics at basin scale

Snowmelt 2021 was representative of all melting periods occurring since 1987. Despite being the second coldest snowmelt recorded in the monitoring period, the water discharge, precipitation, and suspended sediment transport remained consistent with the values registered in the previous decades. The precipitation (210.8 mm) and water discharge ($0.52 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$) values observed in 2021 fall within the ranges recorded since 1987, which varied from 164 mm to 533 mm and from $0.12 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ to $0.70 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, respectively. Additionally, the suspended sediment load for 2021 was monitored at 20 t km^{-2} . Considering the different sediment dynamics observed in the past along the Rio Cordon, Rainato et al. (2017) identified three spans in the long-term monitoring, i.e., 1986–1993, 1994–2002, and 2003–2014, reporting mean snowmelt suspended sediment amounts equal to 24.8, 39.9, and $26.8 \text{ t km}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, respectively. Therefore, the suspended sediment load recorded in snowmelt 2021 was in line with that measured in 1986–1993 and 2003–2014, i.e., periods of ordinary sediment dynamics and fluxes, and differing from that observed in 1994–2002, which exhibited an almost double suspended load. In the Rio Cordon basin, the period 1994–2002 was a period of intensified sediment fluxes due to the effects induced by the large and infrequent September 1994 flood. This event activated several sediment source areas throughout the basin and strongly altered the Rio Cordon stream, by removing bedforms and armour layer. Such conditions favoured high sediment availability for about a decade (1994–2002), during which the sediment fluxes were found to be increased (Rainato et al., 2017). Interestingly, the snowmelt 2021 clearly differs in terms of suspended load from the period 1994–2002, and this despite the distance of only two years from the exceptional October 2018 flood, which altered the stream network even more extensively than the September 1994 event (Rainato et al., 2021; Pellegrini et al. 2023). Therefore, the results obtained during the snowmelt 2021 seem to suggest that the Rio Cordon reacted differently to the large and infrequent events that affected it. Whereas the September 1994

Fig. 8. Graph illustrating the overlapping dynamics between the percentage of snow cover on sediment source areas for each sub-basin (primary Y-axis, lines) and the transported suspended sediment load during the snowmelt period (secondary Y-axis, bars).

induced an alteration on sediment dynamics and fluxes over the long-term, i.e., a memory effect (sensu Rainato et al., 2017; Rickenmann, 2020), the October 2018 seems to have influenced the sediment transport processes on shorter timescales. Such hypothesis agrees with the analysis of suspended sediment fluxes over the period 2020 – 2021, which demonstrated, already two years after the October 2018 flood, a progressive reduction of sediment supply from the windthrow areas and then, a suspended sediment load decrease (Pellegrini et al., 2023). This sediment fluxes restore was accompanied by a rapid bedform re-stabilization, with the recovery of step-pool configuration (Pellegrini et al., 2021). Although the 2021 snowmelt season in the Rio Cordon was ordinary, the catchment sediment transport processes typically differ significantly from those observed in other European basins. In western Norway, sediment transport in glacierized catchments like Erdalen (79.5 km²) and Bødalen (60.1 km²) is primarily driven by seasonal snowmelt, which typically begins in March or April and can last until July at the highest elevations. During the spring months (April–June), increased runoff is mainly thermally driven by rising air temperatures, with relatively low precipitation leading to moderate increases in suspended sediment concentrations (Beylich et al., 2017). In contrast, sediment transport in the Izas catchment (0.33 km²), in the central Pyrenees, showed processes similar to those in the Rio Cordon, with significant influence from snowmelt dynamics, particularly during the second phase of the snowmelt period. During this time, as more of the catchment becomes snow-free, moderate discharge increases occur due to day-night temperature fluctuations and rainfall (Lana-Renault et al., 2011). In the Iberian Peninsula, large basins such as the Ésera (1484 km²) and Siurana (610 km²) display distinct sediment transport dynamics influenced by sediment availability, as observed during the 2012–2013 period. In fact, Lobera et al. (2016) identified different responses to snowmelt. In the Ésera River, which experiences significant snowmelt during the spring due to high runoff volumes, the sediment dynamics were comparable to those observed in the Rio Cordon. Specifically, both catchments showed similar behaviour in terms of runoff generation and sediment transport during snowmelt events, underscoring the consistency of these processes across different mountainous environments. Additionally, the suspended sediment concentrations (SSC) were also comparable, with SSC_{max} values of 0.21 g l⁻¹ in the Ésera River and 0.16 g l⁻¹ in the Rio Cordon, reinforcing the similarity in sediment dynamics between the two catchments. Conversely, the Siurana basin, characterized as a limited supply system, consistently showed low SSCs (SSC_{max} = 0.01 g l⁻¹) regardless of flood magnitude, reflecting its limited sediment availability.

4.2. Snowmelt sediment dynamics at a finer spatial and temporal scale

Rain-on-snow conditions triggered two main events in May 2021, a month identified as the primary ablation period featuring mean daily temperatures ranging from 1.8 °C to 7.3 °C and cumulative precipitation of 131.6 mm. During this month, the mean suspended sediment flux at the outlet was approximately 3.8 kg ha⁻¹ d⁻¹, with the second week heavily weighting this value as it registered as high sediment contribution (7.39 kg ha⁻¹ d⁻¹). The hysteresis loops comparing the weeks, suggest that the sediment availability was higher than the transport capacity at the beginning of the ablation, probably due to an excess of sediment availability in the main channel after previous floods. Conversely, during the final two weeks, opposite dynamics were observed, suggesting a reduction of sediment availability due to its transport during the first two weeks characterized by more intense precipitation (3_h and 24_h). This condition aligns with the findings of Wu and Fang (2024), who emphasized that precipitation intensity on the snowpack accelerates water infiltration, consequently leading to an increase in surface runoff and, thus, soil erosion (i.e., sediment yield). Therefore, the high precipitation intensities of the initial two weeks, resulting in a peak in sediment transport, suggested (i) a hypothetical sediment depletion along the sediment sources and hillslopes of the

tributaries and (ii) a likely increase in sediment deposition along the main channel. This process reached its apex in week 4, when the highest amount of cumulative precipitation contributed to the sediment flushing and thus to the peak of sediment concentration at the outlet of the basin. Existing literature underscores that the potential of river reaches to store and release sediments is influenced by sediment supply, flood events, slope, and channel confinement (Hinderer 2001; Mao et al., 2010). A steeper slope, for instance, results in higher shear stresses, limiting sediment storage. Similarly, a more confined channel, characterized by a smaller width/depth ratio, exhibits elevated shear stresses at the same discharge, enhancing sediment transport efficiency and reducing the likelihood of sediment storage (Mao et al. 2009). Thus, further investigation into the geometry, detailed topography and hydraulic characteristics of each reach could provide valuable insights into the interplay between slope, confinement, and the temporal dynamics of water discharge and sediment transport (Buendia et al., 2016; Hassan et al., 2005). These dynamics could also explain the tendency of reaches' deposition in the former part of the month and of erosion during the latter. Similar processes were verified also during the three days of the main event occurred in the second week suggesting an excess of sediment availability over the transport capacity during the raising limb and the opposite during the falling. This was confirmed by the daily budget analysis at event-scale. Although hysteresis analysis has been and is still widely used in literature (Williams, 1989; Lenzi and Marchi, 2000; Gao and Josefson, 2012; Yeshaneh et al., 2014), the direct link between hysteresis pattern and processes responsible for those are still rather vague. Indeed, these would depend on the size, degree of activity, connectivity, and temporal activity of sediment sources at the scale of the basin and will depend on the processes of storage/remobilization of sediments stored along the river network and hillslopes, which is still difficult to quantify at short temporal scales. In this study, by ascertaining the amount and temporal variability of sediment storage and remobilization over different portions of the channel network and at different time scales, it has been possible to describe in detail the different responses and dynamics of the suspended sediment fluxes along a mountain basin during the ablation season.

4.3. Sediment sources contribution

Although T1 and T2 exhibit the highest numbers and larger total areas of sediment sources (see section 3.4), the overall coverage of sediment sources (%) was lower compared to T3 and T4. In fact, their relative contribution to suspended sediment loads changed slightly over time, as the area of T1 remained stable in terms of snow cover, whereas T2 and especially T3 and T4 consistently increased in contributing sediment source size as snow disappeared from the sub-basins along the ablation season. The topographical features of the Rio Cordon basin further supported this observation, particularly because the upper part is virtually disconnected to the lower part of the basin (Cavalli et al., 2016). This disconnection is primarily attributed to a hanging valley (Martini et al., 2022) in the upper part of the basin (Fig. 1 and Fig. 6), within which T4 is mainly situated. Related to this, past literature has also identified inefficient sediment transfer within the stream network in the upper plateau (Oss Cazzador et al., 2021), which underscores once again the limited chances for in-channel or hillslope sediment sources to reach the outlet (Dalla Fontana and Marchi, 2003). Also, the nature of sediment sources is believed to have played a crucial role, with T1 and T2 characterized by landslides, while T3 and T4 are predominantly associated with debris flow channels (Martini et al., 2022). Notably, a previous investigation by Rainato et al. (2018) in the same basin (1994–2006) indicated that landslides had minimal impact on suspended sediment transport. Nonetheless, the grain size distribution related to the transported material within the sub-basins provides strong evidence supporting the fact that the grain sizes of the suspended sediment material is notably finer in the downstream sub-basins (T3 and T4) associated with debris flow channels compared to the upstream sub-

basins (T1 and T2) hosting both landslides and debris flow channels. Despite this, worth mentioning is the fact that the debris flow channels are more directly connected to the channel network, facilitating sediment transport, particularly during the melting phase or similar events like rain-on-snow, making them a more effective source compared to landslides. In fact, as well documented in [Martini et al. \(2022\)](#), field evidence confirms that in both T3 and T4, the two debris flow channels are functionally connected to the main channel. However, given the unique dynamics of the snowmelt season, further analysis is imperative to verify and comprehend the dynamics and contributions of sediment sources across different seasons and event scales. This understanding holds particular importance in the context of climate change, guiding plans for future sustainable management strategies. Nonetheless, the altitude and exposure of the basins (Tab. 1) suggest that T3 and T4, characterized by lower elevations (outlet at 1920 and 1830 m a.s.l., respectively) and southeast to east exposure, may have facilitated a more rapid snowmelt ([Harms and Chanasyk, 2012](#)). This dynamic, together with those previously mentioned (i.e., snow cover, type of sediment source and GSD) could have contributed to increase sediment delivery, significantly influencing sediment transport patterns. Notably, the observed inverse relationship between snow cover and sediment contribution underscores the significance of snow in mitigating erosion. Our results align with the findings of [Lana-Renault et al. \(2011\)](#), suggesting that the reduction in snow cover exposes soil to precipitation in May and June, lead to increased erosion and suspended sediment transport. This also agrees with earlier studies in the Rocky Mountains by [Williams et al. \(1996\)](#) and [Baron et al. \(2000\)](#), highlighting the susceptibility of alpine streams to substantial hydro-chemical changes in response to even minor shifts in climate. These findings emphasize the strong interplay between snow dynamics and sediment transport, which should be further explored considering the potential effects induced by climate change on the mountain basins.

4.4. Future challenges and perspectives

Our analysis, conducted at a small scale with a dense network of high-frequency monitoring, furthers our knowledge on sediment cascade in snowmelt dynamics. However, advancing our understanding of snowmelt-driven hydrological and sedimentological dynamics requires addressing additional challenges, with new directions for future research. Integrating advanced remote sensing technologies such as satellite imagery and LiDAR data could offer a powerful means to characterize snow cover extent, identify sediment sources, and monitor morphological changes more accurately. Thirdly, field-based data, such as those collected in this study, could play a crucial role in advancing modelling approaches that integrate meteorological, hydrological, and sedimentological processes to simulate the complex dynamics of snowmelt-induced sediment transport ([Battista et al., 2020](#); [Huang et al., 2024](#); [Wu and Fang, 2024](#)), particularly, in the context of a changing climate scenario. Lastly, establishing long-term in-depth monitoring networks would be crucial for tracking the evolving dynamics of snowmelt over extended periods. Thus, by systematically tracking changes in snowmelt patterns and sediment transport regimes, we could detect emerging trends, identify critical thresholds, and provide more effective management practices. Moreover, expanding our studies across different mountain basins and climates will enable us to capture the diverse variability of snowmelt processes. However, scaling up this methodology to larger areas poses several challenges. As the scale of the study area increases, it encompasses a broader range of elevations, which introduces significant variability in snowpack depth, land use patterns (e.g., forest cover, bare soil, urban areas), topography, and climatic conditions such as temperature and precipitation. These last two factors are expected to fluctuate even more rapidly in a changing climate, potentially causing more pronounced shifts within a single large basin. Nonetheless, larger basins may also experience more diverse snowmelt patterns, varied sediment sources, and the presence of

channel control works, which may influence even more sediment dynamics downstream. These structures (e.g., check dams and channel lining) can alter the natural flow of water and sediments, potentially disrupting the transport processes studied in smaller and more natural systems, such as the Rio Cordon basin. Therefore, while the methodology is adaptable to larger scales, it requires meticulous planning and adjustment to account for additional variables. Effective upscaling necessitates a comprehensive consideration of how these factors interact and impact sediment transport, demanding a tailored approach to fieldwork and data interpretation to ensure accurate and meaningful results. Recent advances in high-resolution spatial and temporal interpretation of satellite images, aided by AI (e.g., Planet Labs and Google Earth Engine), improved the reliability of cheap turbidity sensors that can now be deployed in denser networks (e.g., [Droujko and Molnar, 2022](#)), and progress in citizen science approaches for gathering spatially distributed datasets of discharge and suspended sediment (e.g., [Njue et al., 2021](#)) are likely to facilitate the upscaling of the approach presented in this paper to larger basins. To support this upscaling, strategies could include identifying sample areas that drain regions with characteristics similar to those previously mentioned and examining areas both upstream and downstream of in-channel structures.

5. Conclusions

This study on sediment dynamics during the 2021 snowmelt period in the Rio Cordon basin identified key outcomes regarding the interactions among sediment availability, transport capacity, and hydro-meteorological influences on the sediment cascade.

i) Sediment availability and transport capacity exhibited significant variation throughout the snowmelt period: in the initial two weeks, sediment availability exceeded transport capacity, while in the subsequent two weeks, transport capacity exceeded sediment availability. This pattern was also observed in the analysis of the main snowmelt event, where sediment transport was limited during the rising limb and transport capacity increased during the falling limb, highlighting the dynamic nature of snowmelt-related sediment transport;

ii) Hysteresis analysis proved to be valuable in detecting shifts in longitudinal (tributary-main channel) suspended sediment connectivity throughout the snowmelt period;

iii) Variations in snow cover over the sediment sources and across different sub-basins significantly influenced the sediment supply;

iv) The integration of high-resolution data sources, including sensors, water and sediment samples, satellite imagery, and sediment source inventories, enabled a detailed and comprehensive understanding of sediment dynamics in the basin;

Overall, these findings provide valuable insights into sediment dynamics in mountainous regions and can inform more effective management strategies for mountain basins, especially considering accelerated snowmelt and reduced snowpack depth due to climate change.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

G. Pellegrini: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **L. Mao:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **R. Rainato:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **L. Martini:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **L. Picco:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence

the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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